

SPECTRUM EXPLAINABILITY

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SPECTRUM

- Extremely valuable *natural resource* in high demand
- Spectrum efficiency key to success of 6G
- Limited understanding of usage
- Increased spectrum sharing necessary
- How to identify sharing opportunities?
 - Frequency, space, time
 - Understanding dynamics of spectrum use critical
 - Measurements provide key insight
- Steep learning curve

UNITED STATES FREQUENCY ALLOCATIONS THE RADIO SPECTRUM

AI EXPLAINABILITY PRINCIPLES

- Explanation
 - System delivers or contains accompanying evidence or reason(s) for outputs and/or processes
- Meaningful
 - Systems provide explanations that are understandable to the intended consumer(s)
- Explanation Accuracy
 - An explanation correctly reflects the reason for generating the output and/or accurately reflects the system's process
- Knowledge Limits
 - A system only operates under conditions for which it was designed and when the system reaches a sufficient confidence in its output

Principles depend on AI use situation and may include regulator and legal requirements, quality control and customer relations

AI/ML MODELS

- How do we know the conditions for which the models are designed?
 - Depends on the data (i.e. what data were the models trained on?)
 - How was the data collected?
 - Who collected the data
 - Who funded data collection
 - What cases/dynamics/behavior does the data cover?
 - How is the data distributed across instances?
 - Etc.

Datasheets for datasets¹ provides general template for documenting datasets

1. Timnit Gebru, Jamie Morgenstern, Briana Vecchione, Jennifer Wortman Vaughan, Hanna Wallach, Hal Daumé III, and Kate Crawford. 2021. Datasheets for datasets. *Commun. ACM* 64, 12 (December 2021), 86–92.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3458723>

AI/ML MODEL LIMITATIONS

- Why does model fail/make a mistake?
 - An input that the model was not trained on is received
- What happens when the model sees a "new" input?
 - Output is unpredictable
- What happens when model doesn't work properly?
 - Incorrect decision
 - Consequences?
- Who is harmed?
 - Important question
 - Those not represented in the data
 - Marginalized groups

EXAMPLE – SPEECH RECOGNITION

- Limited set of languages
- “As more devices embed speech as a mode of communication using standard accents, speakers who cannot or will not assimilate will continue to be marginalized”¹

1. Halcyon Lawrence, Siri Disciplines, Your Computer is on Fire

EXAMPLE – FACIAL RECOGNITION

- Commercial tools have poor performance on darker skin
- Benchmark datasets
 - From web
 - Not representative
- www.gendershades.org
- Banned in many places
 - Still everywhere

Gender Shades: Intersectional Accuracy Disparities in Commercial Gender Classification
<http://proceedings.mlr.press/v81/buolamwini18a/buolamwini18a.pdf>

EXAMPLE – LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS¹

- Large training data sets from web crawling
 - Who is represented on web?
 - Larger data not necessarily better/more comprehensive
- Results in models that “encode stereotypical and derogatory associations along gender, race, ethnicity and disability status”
- “Feeding AI systems on the world’s beauty, ugliness, and cruelty, but expecting it to reflect only the beauty is a fantasy.”²

1. Emily M. Bender, Timnit Gebru, Angelina McMillan-Major, and Shmargaret Shmitchell. 2021. On the Dangers of Stochastic Parrots: Can Language Models Be Too Big? 🐦 In Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '21). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 610–623. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442188.3445922>
2. Ruha Benjamin. 2019. Race After Technology.

DATA IS NOT NEUTRAL

- The conceptual, practical, and ethical issues surrounding data begin at the moment of collection
- Data collection is a result of human decisions
 - What to collect?/What not to collect?
 - How to collect?
- There is an invisible (direct or indirect) relationship between the collector and the collectee
 - Power dynamics

Mimi Onuoha, "The Point of <https://points.datasociety.net/the-point-of-collection-8ee44ad7c2fa#.2m7wj69bv>

SPECTRUM EXPLAINABILITY

- Broadly understanding how spectrum is being used across frequency, space, time
 - Complex, multidisciplinary question
 - Allocation for service(s)
 - Organizations/Licenses
 - Antennas
 - Transmitters/Receivers
 - Human protocols
 - What is spectrum being used for?
 - How is spectrum being used?
 - Human activity driving spectrum use
- Accessible to variety of stakeholders
- Improved understanding of spectrum datasets

APPROACH

- Spectrum Knowledge Graph
 - Graph models of information from different sources
 - Contextual information
 - Measurement summaries
 - Unified query interface
 - Connect information across models
 - Implemented on Neo4j graph database platform
 - Property graph model
 - Cypher query language

INFORMATION SOURCES MODELED

- **Context**
 - US Spectrum Allocation table
 - Service(s) allocated per frequency band
 - FCC License databases
 - Organization licensed to use frequency
 - Antenna details
 - Location
 - Time period
 - Radioreference.com
 - Organizational and functional use
 - Crowdsourced
 - Events
 - Planned
 - Unplanned
- **Measurements**
 - Measurement system
 - Components
 - Configuration
 - Location
 - Measurement summaries
 - Daily statistics
 - Occupancy
 - Change detection
 - Trends

IIT SPECTRUM OBSERVATORY

- General purpose wideband monitoring since mid-2007
 - 30 MHz – 6 GHz
 - Lower resolution
 - Each sweep takes ~ minute
 - ~ 93 MB data/day
- Special purpose monitoring since Oct 2017 (44MHz-1GHz)
 - Public Safety communications
 - Federal, state and local
 - Industrial/Business
 - Higher resolution monitoring
 - Multiple sweeps/sec
 - ~ 23 GB data/day
- Energy sensing

QUERIES

- Create new graphs and connections between information sources
- Connect interesting features in data to explanatory information
- Ex.
 - Connect changes in spectrum occupancy to events
 - Chicago White Sox spectrum use connected to baseball games at home stadium
 - What spectrum occupancy changes connected to Covid 19 lockdowns
 - IIT campus frequencies
 - Identify allocation and license information for measured frequencies
 - Identify measured frequencies with antennas in range of spectrum observatory

SUMMARY – SPECTRUM EXPLAINABILITY

- Spectrum Knowledge Graph prototype created
 - Contextual information and measurement summaries modeled and implemented in Neo4j
 - 440,000+ nodes
 - 24,900,000+ relationships
 - Graph models flexible
 - Easily modified/refined
- Queries used to retrieve variety of information
- Help put measurements into context
 - Better understand measurement data
 - Answer questions to identify limitations of data
 - Potential to improve
 - Measurement
 - Modeling
- Reduce learning curve
 - Make spectrum domain and spectrum measurements more accessible to variety of stakeholders

SUMMARY – GENERAL

- AI can have significant impact in 5G, 6G
- Explainability will be limiting factor
 - Identifying knowledge limits
 - Understanding dataset
- More focus and effort needed
 - Data collection
 - Data curation
 - Data understanding and documentation
- Different expertise needed as part of team
 - Social science
 - History
 - Policy
 - Etc.
- Need to change underlying models in society to make significant change

THANK YOU

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